

POLAC JOURNAL OF SOCIAL AND MANAGEMENT SCIENCES (PJSMS)

Vol. 3 No. 2 September, 2025

ISSN - Print: 2992-5009; Online: 2437-1246

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Impact of Demographic Factors on Tax Compliance in Nigeria's Informal Sector: The Case Study of the South-South Geopolitical Zone

POLAC Journal of
Social and Management Sciences
2025, Vol. 3 (2), 227 – 245
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Nigeria Police Academy, Kano.
pjsms@gmail.com
DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17792729

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Abstract

This study is aimed at investigating the demographic factors that can influence informal sector operators' tax compliance behaviour in Nigeria. The focus is on the South-South geopolitical zone in Nigeria. The study investigated to know if there is a relationship between demographic factors (gender, age, education, employment status and residential location) and informal sector operators' tax compliance. To actualize these objectives, 650 questionnaires were administered to the respondents in the geopolitical zone as follows: Rivers State-120, Delta State-120, Edo State-110, Cross River State-100, Bayelsa State-100 and Akwa-Ibom State-100. A total of 390 of the questionnaires were duly completed and returned from the geopolitical zone, resulting in a 60% response rate. The study employed the application of the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) and econometric techniques. The economic techniques involve descriptive statistics, correlation and regression used in analysing the data obtained. The results of the tests of the hypotheses suggest that a non-significant negative relationship exists between gender and informal sector operators' tax compliance, between age and informal sector operators' tax compliance and between residential location/government presence and informal sector operators' tax compliance. While a positive significant relationship exists between education and informal sector operators' tax compliance, and between employment status and informal sector operators' tax compliance. The implication of this is that demographic factors such as education and employment status can positively influence the compliance behaviour of informal sector operators' taxpayers. Therefore, it was recommended amongst others that tax education should be incorporated in secondary and tertiary institutions' syllabi to inculcate the culture of paying taxes in the students who are future potential taxpayers, and the enforcement of the tax laws by the relevant tax authority on tax evaders.

Keywords: Demographic, Informal Sector, Compliance, Tax, Taxpayers.

Article history:

Received: 18 December 2024

Reviewed: 20 February 2025

Accepted: 29 March 2025

About the Journal: PJSMS is a multidisciplinary journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil-Kano, Nigeria, published biannually.

Garuba, A. O. & Eichie, D. (2025).

Impact of Demographic Factors on Tax Compliance in Nigeria's Informal Sector: The Case Study of the South-South Geopolitical Zone.

Introduction

Personal income tax is an obligatory amount imposed by the government on individuals who are employees either in the public or private sector (i.e. under 'pay as you earn'(PAYE) and those running their businesses (self-employed), in partnership or under a business name (i.e. direct tax) as per the Personal Income Tax Act, amended 2011. This tax is a direct form of taxation whose impact is on the taxpayer. Under the direct form of taxation, the burden or incidence of tax is upon the taxpayers who finally bear the money burden and are unable to pass the burden to others (Bhatia, 2008). The personal income tax is one of the ways that state governments can generate revenue internally for development purposes.

Taxation has been highlighted as a means used by the government in both developing and developed countries for funding social amenities and basic infrastructures (Eiya, Ilaboya, & Okoye, 2016). Taxation is also one of the significant ways that a government can boost its internally generated revenue in this era of COVID-19 (coronavirus) pandemic across the globe (Garuba & Eichie, 2022). This can be achieved by the government strengthening its tax system. The main intent of levying certain taxes on the public is to generate revenues for the government for public expenditures (Singn, 1999; Shanmugan, 2003). Other important intents are maintenance of law and order, protection of infant industries, stopping consumption of harmful goods, redistribution of income, correcting unfavourable balance of payments, as a fiscal device, to encourage industrialization, etc. Therefore, it has become imperative for the government to optimize its

tax revenues in order to meet its obligations (Ndekwa,1991).

The world in 2020 witnessed the volatility of oil prices due to the COVID-19 (Coronavirus) pandemic that ravaged the world. The ravaging coronavirus pandemic and the uncertainty in crude oil markets stressed the business cycle of the local and global economy due to the volatility of the prices (Mzoughi, Urom, Uddin, & Guesmi, 2020). The price of oil has been dwindling in the world market, and this is hurting the revenue profile of the country because of its dependence on a single product since the 1970s (Eiya, Ilaboya, & Okoye, 2016). With the increasing cost of governance, increasing depreciation of the Naira to the Dollar and the fluctuation of oil prices in the world market, it has become expedient for the government to look inwards on how to increase its revenue base. Garuba and Oladipupo (2021) opined that the era of mainly depending on revenue allocation by the State governments is gradually phasing out. Hence, most state governments are now looking inwards to improve their internally generated revenue (IGR). The significance of tax revenue to the government cannot be overemphasized.

Tax compliance no doubt improves the revenue base of the government and helps to fund its capital projects, less dependent on a mono-product and foreign aid (Garuba et al., 2022). It should be noted that the aggregate revenue generated from taxation depends on the voluntary tax compliance of the taxpayers (Eshag, 1983). That is, the amount realized or generated by the government from taxation depends on the desire of the taxpayers to improve their society by willingly paying their taxes as patriotic citizens (Eiya et al., 2016). On the other hand, where the taxpayers fail to adhere to the tax laws, it indicates tax non-

compliance. The issue of tax non-compliance has been worrisome in most countries of the world.

The challenging aspect of income tax administration in Nigeria is in the area of collecting tax from operators in the informal sector (Modugu & Omoye, 2014). Tax evasion has been a major issue in emerging economies across the globe. Hence, it is now occupying the front burner of these emerging economies. Therefore, there is a need to improve compliance and bring more taxpayers into the tax net, especially those who have been evading tax. No doubt improved tax compliance would help the government to increase its revenue base and finance its basic infrastructures. Therefore, the objective of this study is to empirically examine the impact of demographic factors on tax compliance in Nigeria's Informal Sector: The case study of the South-South geopolitical zone.

The study focuses on the self-employed who are unregistered and unregulated operators in the informal sector. The informal sector involves activities or sources of income that are not fully regulated by the government and, in most cases, escape detection in the official estimates of tax administration and gross domestic product (GDP). The justification for the informal sector is due to the lack of an accurate database and the untaxed incomes due to tax evasion in that sector. Against the above backdrop, we hypothesized in the null form the following:

- i. There is no significant correlation between gender and informal sector operators' tax compliance.
- ii. There is no significant correlation between age and informal sector operators' tax compliance.
- iii. There is no significant correlation between education and informal sector operators' tax compliance.

- iv. There is no significant correlation between employment status and informal sector operators' tax compliance; and
- v. There is no significant correlation between residential location/government presence and informal sector operators' tax compliance.

Literature Review

This section appraises extant literature on demographic factors and taxpayers' compliance behaviour. It begins with a conceptual framework and appraisal of the related literature, personal income tax, tax compliance and the informal sector. The section concludes with the theoretical framework that forms the foundation of the study.

The Concept of Tax

Governments have the responsibility of providing social infrastructure in return for taxes collected from their citizens (Garuba & Mamudu, 2023). Such infrastructures require huge capital outlays, which are financed by taxation and other revenue sources. According to Anyaduba and Okoye (2015) government relies heavily on its tax-based revenue to fulfil most of its numerous responsibilities and obligations, ranging from the provision of pipe-borne water, electricity, schools, hospitals, roads, bridges, dams, etc., to security and the rule of law.

Tolby (1978) describes the tax system as a worldwide apparatus whereby the state imposes a statutory levy on its citizens for the benefit of society. Akanle (1991) defines taxation more generally as "a compulsory levy imposed on a subject or upon his property by government having authority over him". This definition reflects a wider base of taxation, as tax may be charged not only upon people but also upon properties and transactions to raise money for public purposes. Anyaduba (2000) states that tax is an obligatory levy imposed by the government on the profit,

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

wealth/income of either an individual or a corporate body for a public purpose. From the definitions given above, three essential characteristics of a tax can be deduced: Firstly, it is an obligatory levy. Secondly, the government imposes taxes. Thirdly, the revenue generated should be for public purposes. These definitions show that not all internally generated revenues of the government are taxes. That is, not all government revenues are compulsory levies. For instance, some charges are imposed rather by way of penalties or fees. The revenue generated from the fine paid for wrong parking or for beating a traffic light is not a tax. Also, revenue realized from tolls or payment for specific services is not considered as tax but just a levy.

A taxpayer cannot sue the government for not spending enough tax money in his locality, even when he pays more tax than others (Garuba & Eichie, 2023). The government's authority to levy is not dependent on the conferment of a benefit but on its sovereign power.

Personal Income Tax (PIT)

Personal income tax is an obligatory amount imposed on individuals who are employees either in the private or public sector, and the self-employed running their business under a business name or partnership (i.e. organised) and the unregistered and unregulated operators by the government. The Personal Income Tax (Amendment) Act (PITA) 2011 consists of two forms. They are: (i) Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE), meant for those in paid employment either in the private or public sector; and (ii) Taxes for the self-employed, which consist of those who own and run organised businesses and the unregistered and unregulated operators in the informal sector. Under PAYE, the employers are charged with the responsibility of deducting taxes from the monthly salaries of their staff and remitting

the same to the appropriate tax authority. Where the employer fails to deduct or remit deductions from employees to the appropriate tax authorities, such employers shall be subjected to a fine on conviction of ₦5,000, and in addition, ₦100 daily for the period of the failure, together with the principal amount (Personal Income Tax (Amendment) Act, 2011). This type of tax is a direct method of taxing employees and business owners. The impact of the tax is on the taxpayer, who cannot shift the burden to other people.

In Nigeria, tax administration is bestowed on the three levels of government. Tax is critical to income generation and fiscal policy. PITA (2011) imposes tax on individuals and unincorporated bodies. The 1999 Nigerian constitution gave the federal government exclusive legislative jurisdiction on virtually all taxes. The federal government collects income tax from companies, hydrocarbon tax and the personal income tax of citizens residing in the Federal Capital Territory, employees of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, expatriates and Nigerians residing abroad but earning income in Nigeria. Civilians who are working in the military formations and the police force pay their taxes to their respective internal revenue services of the states where they reside. The responsibility of collecting personal income tax from residents in a state who are employees of federal, state, local government, private sector, and those who own their own business (self-employed) rests with the State Internal Revenue Service (IRS).

Tax Compliance

The aim of imposing tax laws is to achieve compliance with them. Kirchler (2007) states that compliance is either willingly or imposed. Tax compliance is when a taxpayer pays his tax based on the correct declaration, computes his tax liability and files his returns on time (Brown & Mazur, 2005). According to Thuronyi (2003), tax compliance consists of

accurately stating all assessable income, payment of the assessed tax liability timely without a reminder from tax officials and filing tax returns. Garuba (2021) avers that tax compliance is the capability of taxpayers to conform to relevant laws without any compulsion.

Literature on compliance behaviour highlights, among others, the important role of demographic variables in taxpayers' behaviour. Generally, demographic factors such as gender, age, education, employment status and residential location could influence tax compliance. The probability that a taxpayer is compliant is shaped by the following variables: tax rate, income level, moral and attitude (psychological factors) and demographic factors such as age and gender (Brooks, 2001). According to Aruwa and Oklobia (2014), there is an argument that voluntary tax compliance is the key to any country's revenue growth. These arguments are centred on the belief that the more taxpayers are willing to remit more taxes, the more the government can provide basic amenities to the citizens, but this may not be sustained in a country where there is a high level of corruption (Garuba et al., 2022). In fact, taxation is the key to the survival of most economies, particularly the developing nations. Therefore, every committed government must strive to attain tax compliance.

Gender and Tax Compliance

Gender implies the characteristics that distinguish between men and women, which reflect one's biological sex or gender identity (Sari & Supadmi, 2014). Gender is a key factor that influences taxpayers' behaviour and compliance attitude (Jackson & Milliron, 1986). Prior studies show a correlation between gender and tax compliance. However, the findings vary and are inconsistent. Some of the studies found male

taxpayers to be less tax compliant than female taxpayers. This position was espoused in the work of Tittle (1980). This is because women, by their nature, are more moral, conservative, and conforming and therefore, are more tax compliant than their male counterparts (Jackson & Milliron, 1986). Olowookere and Fasina (2013) concurred with Jackson and Milliron that traditionally, females are conformists, ethical and conservative in their lifestyle. Therefore, the female taxpayers are more tax compliant than their male counterparts. However, the work of Houston and Tran (2001) showed a contrary result that females are less tax compliant than males. Richardson (2006) posits that gender does not influence tax compliance based on a study carried out across 45 countries. He therefore opined that there is no correlation between gender and compliance. Alabede (2014) agreed with Richardson that gender does not significantly impact the tax compliance behaviour of taxpayers in Nigeria. In summary, it shows that the effect of gender on taxpayers' compliance behaviour is inconsistent.

Age and Tax Compliance

Most of the studies in the United States of America (USA) portray age as a vital variable in explaining taxpayers' compliance behaviour. For instance, a study by Clotfelter (1983) revealed there is an intimate correlation between age and compliance. However, there are studies that researched age as a demographic variable, but their results were inconsistent (Tittle, 1980; Warneryd & Walerud, 1982; Christian & Gupta, 1992; Beron, Tuachen & Witte, 1992). Some researchers argue that youthful taxpayers are less tax compliant than adult taxpayers. Tittle (1980) agrees to this assertion because the youths are usually daring in taking risks and do not care about penalties. There is also a study that showed a significant association

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

exists between age and compliance (Jackson & Milliron, 1986).

On the contrary, there are studies that revealed there is no relationship between age and compliance, that is, adults are less compliant than youths (Warneryd & Walerud, 1982; Wahlund, 1992). Torgler (2004) also averred that adults are less tax compliant than the youths. Engida and Baisa (2014) carried out their research in Ethiopia, and the result revealed that adults are less compliant than youths. However, studies also showed there is no relationship between age and compliance (Spicer & Becker, 1980; Porcano, 1988). From the foregoing, it shows that the results from various studies are contradictory. Therefore, there is a need for further investigation.

Education and Tax Compliance

The level of education in general, awareness and tax knowledge today occupies the front burner of most nations of the world because it helps to shape the level of compliance of the taxpayers. The result of the work of Chen (2006) in Malaysia showed that education is important in improving voluntary compliance. Singh (2003) posits that a substantial relationship exists between general knowledge and comprehension of laws by the taxpayers and their level of tax compliance. Also, Komhauser (2007) posits that taxpayers' compliance behaviour can be improved where efforts are geared towards all segments of the population. So, the relationship exists between knowledge and compliance (Lewis, 1982).

Mohd (2010) states that tax knowledge is essential in promoting public awareness of tax laws as an instrument of national development, and letting the citizens know how much is collected and expended. It is important to educate potential taxpayers on the need to pay their taxes, especially in emerging economies. This can be achieved via dialogue sessions, seminars or review of

secondary school syllabus with the introduction of taxation as a subject (Mohani, 2001). No doubt greater education has a substantial association with compliance (Chan, Troutman & O'Bryan, 2000). When taxpayers are educated, they understand the effect of tax evasion on the economy and become more disposed to greater compliance. Mohd (2010) highlighted that taxpayers who are exposed to better tax knowledge through seminars, tax sensitization, etc., develop a compliance attitude than those taxpayers who lack exposure.

On the contrary, an insignificant relationship exists between education and compliance behaviour of taxpayers (Richardson, 2008; Collins, Milliron, & Toy, 1992). Also, Alabede (2014) posits that education does not significantly impact taxpayers' compliance behaviour in Nigeria. McGee and Tyler (2006) argue that people with less education are inclined to be more compliant than their better-educated counterparts. The reason could be that they may not want to run afoul of the tax law with its attendant negative consequences (Garuba et al., 2023). The findings of the studies above produced mixed results as regards the correlation between education and compliance.

Based on the literature reviewed, it showed the impact of education on tax compliance is ambiguous. The ambiguity is as result of the inability to ascertain the segment of education being measured at a point in time. However, four measures identified from the literature review are: the general degree of fiscal knowledge; knowledge involving evasion opportunities; general education attainment; and specific tax knowledge. The measurements highlighted above help to address the ambiguity regarding the effect of education on compliance. Therefore, the correlation that exists between education and compliance is inconsistent. Apart from a

positive correlation, it was also found negative relationship exists between education and compliance. Thus, it is evident from extant literature on tax compliance, especially those on demographic variables, that there is a need for further research in this area. It is also evident that the mixed results are due to employing different variables and operationalization of those variables.

Employment Status and Tax Compliance

Employment is a key basis of assessable income (Garuba et al., 2022). Tax non-compliance is more likely in self-employment occupations such as sole proprietorship and partnership (Chau & Leung, 2009). Andreoni, Erard and Feinstein (1998) averred that a greater percentage of sole proprietors are involved in the understatement of taxes. However, employment is the key basis of assessable income. Assessable income could be derived from paid employment or self-employment. However, self-employment occupation income is more susceptible to under-reporting than income from employment occupation for tax purposes (Alabede, 2014).

For instance, under Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE), employers are expected to deduct tax at source from their employees' salaries and remit the same to the relevant tax authority. Employers under PAYE are charged with the responsibility of deducting taxes from the monthly salaries of their staff and forwarding the same to the appropriate body. Where an employer fails to deduct or remit deductions from employees to the appropriate tax authorities within the stipulated time, such employer shall be liable to a fine as stated in the Act. That is, N5,000 on conviction, plus N100 for each day the failure lasts, in addition to the principal amount to be remitted. However, this amount is too meagre for now and calls for a review. This arrangement reduces the rate of tax non-compliance.

However, empirical evidence revealed mixed results. The study of Greoland and Veldhoren (1983) is in accord with the assertion that the self-employed are more inclined to evasion. It was also observed that employees subjected to payment of withholding tax have fewer opportunities to be non-compliant (Fjeldstad & Semboja, 2001). The study carried out in New Zealand showed employment status has a statistical impact on evasion (Gupta, 2009). While the study of Alabede (2014) in Nigeria found that correlation exists between demographic variables such as age, gender and employment status and compliance. Contrarily, the findings of the study of Birch, Peters and Sawyer (2003) showed that an insignificant relationship exists between employment status and evasion. The study of Manaf, Hasseldine and Hodger (2005) revealed that the self-employed are likely to be more tax compliant. It should be noted that it is the organised self-employed aspect that is referred to here and not the unregistered and unregulated operators in the informal sector. It therefore shows that the self-employed consists of two aspects, namely: (1) the organised self-employed individuals, such as practising professional accountants, architects, engineers, lawyers, etc. and (2) the unregistered and unregulated operators in the informal sector. This second aspect is the focus of this study.

Residential Location and Government Presence.

According to Okoye and Odia (2012), when the government fails to provide basic infrastructures, it may aggravate tax evasion. Taxpayers' compliance behaviour could be influenced by the provision of basic infrastructure by the government, such as hospitals, schools, electricity, good roads and other basic amenities in either the urban or rural locality (Garuba et al., 2023). Individuals perhaps pay their taxes because of the value they attach to the goods the

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

government provides, with the understanding that payments of their taxes not only help in funding the goods and services but also encourage others to pay their taxes (Fjeldstad & Semboja, 2001). Thus, the taxpayers' perception of the provision of basic infrastructures improves tax compliance. This is in line with the theory of fiscal exchange, which advocates that government provision of goods has the tendency to improve compliance.

The dividend of democracy (political slogan) in terms of basic infrastructure and amenities influences the compliance behaviour of the taxpayer positively. This is in line with the theory of fiscal exchange, which advocates that government provision of goods has the tendency to improve compliance. That is, the government can improve compliance via its expenditure because it motivates compliance (Levi, 1988; Moore, 2004). It therefore shows that the taxpayers are mainly interested in the benefits they get in return for payment of taxes.

The informal sector

The economy can be broadly classified into formal and informal sectors. The informal sector generally comprises the economic activities or interactions of individuals, enterprises or other unincorporated entities or organizations, whilst the formal sector represents the economic interactions of organized individual or corporate entities. The term informality means different things to different people. It is characterized by unprotected workers, excessive regulation, low productivity, unfair competition, evasion of the rule of law, underpayment or non-payment of taxes, and work 'underground' or in the shadows." (Perry, Haloney, Arias, Fajnziber, Mason, & Saavedra-Chenduvi, 2007). The International Labour Organisation (ILO, 1972) defines informal enterprise as 'private unincorporated enterprises with five

to ten workers which are not registered with the legislative regulatory Act, as distinct from local regulations governing trade licences or business permits. These enterprises are characterised mainly by small size, non-registration with the regulatory authority, tax evasion and non-compliance with labour laws (ILO, 2010).

The Informal sector is, by nature, heterogeneous and includes business owners and their employees. Business owners are those individuals who work and run their business, such as a professional practice or farming (Fairlie, 2005). The self-employed could also be seen as "persons working for themselves who may or may not employ other workers or members of the family who help to run an enterprise without payment" (Camel, 2000). Such self-employed individuals are regarded as organised self-employed, so they fall outside the informal sector. While the other self-employed are the unregistered and unregulated who operate in the informal sector. According to Onwe (2013), informal employment comprises both self and wage employment that are usually not recognised, regulated or protected by legal or regulatory frameworks. Informal economy categorised as self-employment, including own account workers, heads of family businesses, and unpaid family workers, wage workers, etc. In fact, the informal sector activities range from agricultural production to mining and quarrying, small-scale building and construction, machine shop-manufacturing, traditional Nigerian crafts in clothing and furniture, vehicle and mechanical repair, utility services, and parallel finance structures operating mostly on unwritten rules and providing credit services among others (Uko, Akpanoyoro, & Ekpe, 2020).

The informal sector can also be described as market-based production of goods and services, whether legal or illegal, that escape

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

detection in the official estimates of tax administration and gross domestic product. While for the most part the economic activities of informal workers are legal, they are often not considered in official statistics, and much of the income they generate goes untaxed. However, those who are rationed out of the formal segment could take a job in the (free entry) informal sector.

According to the Bank of Industry (2018), the informal sector comprises any economic activity or source of income that is not fully regulated by the government and other public authorities; this includes enterprises that are not officially registered and lack accurate accounting records, and workers hold jobs lacking critical social or legal protection and employment welfare. Examples of the operators in the informal sector are Street traders, subsistence farmers, small-scale manufacturers, service providers (such as private taxi drivers, carpenters and hairdressers), etc.

Enhancing Financial Innovation and Access (EFInA, 2018) posits that the Nigerian informal sector has a population of 67.2 million. The breakdown of the population is as follows: individual entrepreneurs 36.8 million, business owners with employees 7.5 million and those employed 22.9 million. It shows that the business owners with employees (i.e. 7.5 million) are able to employ 22.9 million staff in the sector. The 'business owners with employees' and the 'employed staff' make up 45% of the total population. Hence, the focus of this study is on the business owners (self-employed) with employees who are the unregistered and unregulated operators in the informal sector.

Methodology

The survey research design was employed in collecting data via a questionnaire in this study. About 650 questionnaires were

administered to informal sector operators in the South-South geographical zone in Nigeria. The South-South geographical zone comprises Akwa-Ibom State, Bayelsa State, Cross River State, Delta State, Edo State and Rivers State. Only 390 questionnaires out of the total of 650 questionnaires administered, representing a 65% response rate, were completed and suitable for use. The questionnaire consists of well-structured closed-ended questions comprising thirty questions using a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. The data obtained was subjected to regression analysis.

Theoretical Framework and Model Specification

A framework for the relationship between demographic factors and informal sector operators' tax compliance behaviour is anchored on Fischer's model, self-employment theory and Fiscal exchange theory. The Fischer's model helps one to understand how the demographic variables such as gender, age, and education influence taxpayers' compliance behaviour. While employment status was adapted from the self-employment theory. The theory indicates that works determine endogenously the proportion of the total workforce that decides to be either an entrepreneur or a worker. On the other hand, residential location or government presence is based on the Fiscal exchange theory. This theory advocates magnitude of government expenditure sways compliance. That is, providing basic infrastructures by governments can improve compliance (Moore, 2004).

Against the backdrop of the above theoretical and empirical review, we propose a functional relationship between gender, age, education, employment status and residential location/government presence; and informal sector operators' tax compliance.

The relationship is depicted schematically as shown below.

Independent Variables

Dependent Variable

Figure 3.1: Schematic representation of the determinants of personal income tax compliance.

Source: Researchers’ Compilation (2024)

Against the above backdrop, it is expected that gender may improve or adversely affect tax compliance. The results of studies carried out on gender as a demographic variable are conflicting. Some of the studies revealed that sex or gender seems to have a substantial influence on compliance, and females are more compliant than their male counterparts because they are averse to risk-taking (Tittle, 1980; Jackson & Milliron, 1986; Hasseldine & Hite, 2007; Olowookere & Fasina, 2013). The results of other researchers showed males are compliant than females because they dare to take risks (Houston & Tran, 2001).

The expected functional correlation between gender and informal sector operators’ tax compliance is as shown below:

$$\text{Informal sector operators tax compliance} = f(\text{gender}) \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

In the same vein, age as a demographic factor may also improve or adversely affect tax compliance. Most of the results of the

research carried out on age as a demographic variable are inconsistent. Some concluded youthful taxpayers are less compliant than adult taxpayers because they are always daring to take risks (Tittle, 1980; Jackson & Milliron, 1986; Wenzel, 2002; Clotfelter, 2003). While others state youthful taxpayers are more compliant than adult taxpayers (Warneryd & Walerud, 1982; Wahlund, 1992; Torgler, 2004; Alabede, 2014). However, an operational correlation is expected between age and personal income tax compliance as:

$$\text{Informal sector operators tax compliance} = f(\text{age}) \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

Results of some research indicate the impact of education on compliance is unclear. Such conflicting results may be due to the complexity of ascertaining which aspect of education is being measured at a point in time. However, little awareness correlates with a negative attitude toward taxation (Lewis, 1982). The findings of Richardson (2008) also

revealed that an insignificant relationship exists between education and compliance. Also, the expected functional correlation exists between education and informal sector operators' tax compliance, as shown below:

$$\text{Informal sector operators tax compliance} = f(\text{education}) \dots \dots \dots (iii)$$

The effect of employment status on informal sector operators' tax compliance is of mixed results. Some studies, such as Gupta (2009) and Alabede (2004), state that employment status is statistically significant in impelling compliance behaviour of taxpayers. Therefore, the expected functional relationship between employment status and informal sector operators' tax compliance is as shown below:

$$\text{Informal sector operators tax compliance} = f(\text{employment status}) \dots \dots \dots (iv)$$

Residential location/Government presence
The provision of basic infrastructure could influence compliance behaviour. The presence of government expenditures, according to fiscal exchange theory, may encourage compliance. That is, the government can improve compliance by providing basic infrastructure in a more

efficient and accessible manner to its citizens (Cowell & Gordon,1988).

$$\text{Informal sector operators tax compliance} = f(\text{residential location/government presence}) \dots \dots \dots (v)$$

Combining equations i-v, we have a general functional form of our equation as:

$$\text{Informal sector operators' tax compliance} = f(\text{gender, age, education, employment status and residential location/government presence}) \dots \dots \dots (v)$$

This is expressed in code form as:

$$ISOTC = f(GE, AG, ED, ES \text{ and } RL)$$

The above equation is expressed in econometric form as:

$$ISOTC = \beta_0 + \beta_1GE + \beta_2AG + \beta_3ED + \beta_3ES + \beta_4RL + e$$

Where

ISOTC = Informal Sector Operators Tax Compliance, GE= Gender, AG= Age, ED= Education, ES= Employment status, RL= Residential Location, β_0 = Unknown coefficient of the variables
e= Error term.

Results and Discussions

This section discusses the findings and discussions of the study.

Table 4.1: Demographic Factors and Informal Sector Operators Tax Compliance Descriptive Statistics

	TC	AGE	EDU	EMP	GEN	RLO
Mean	1.517949	2.353846	4.251282	1.164103	1.397436	1.733333
Median	2.000000	2.000000	4.000000	1.000000	1.000000	2.000000
Maximum	2.000000	4.000000	6.000000	2.000000	2.000000	2.000000
Minimum	1.000000	2.000000	2.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000
Std. Dev.	0.500320	0.567249	0.705058	0.370844	0.489996	0.442785
Skewness	-0.071841	1.351685	-0.131917	1.813855	0.419170	-1.055290
Kurtosis	1.005161	3.838176	3.183511	4.290069	1.175704	2.113636
Jarque-Bera	65.00043	130.1747	1.678375	240.8990	65.50167	85.15302
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.432061	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	592.0000	918.0000	1658.000	454.0000	545.0000	676.0000
Sum Sq. Dev.	97.37436	125.1692	193.3744	53.49744	93.39744	76.26667
Observations	390	390	390	390	390	390

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2024

Table 4.2 Demographic Factors and Informal Sector Operators Tax Compliance Correlation Matrix

	TC	AGE	EDU	EMP	GEN	RLO
TC	1.000000	0.004738	0.052769	0.081070	-0.055388	-0.071172
AGE	0.004738	1.000000	-0.017206	0.004324	-0.044821	0.018423
EDU	0.052769	-0.017206	1.000000	0.018857	-0.014500	-0.023605
EMP	0.081070	0.004324	0.018857	1.000000	-0.034461	-0.030267
GEN	-0.055388	-0.044821	-0.014500	-0.034461	1.000000	0.015798
GOVP	-0.071172	0.018423	-0.023605	-0.030267	0.015798	1.000000

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2024

Gender and Informal Sector Operators' Tax Compliance

The mean value of gender diversity, as shown in Table 4.1, is 1.397, which is quite low. The median value for gender from the said table is 1, which is quite small. The median revealed that there are more males included in the sample than females. The table also showed that the gender diversity had a maximum value of 2 and a minimum value of 1 from the data. The standard deviation from the table is 0.49, which is quite small; hence, the distribution of the score points between males and females was closely distributed around their mean. The results show that gender does not influence informal tax compliance. The correlation results presented in Table 4.2 indicated a very weak negative correlation between tax compliance (TC) and GEN, with a score of -0.055. Moreover, the outcomes showed a very weak negative correlation between GEN and age (AGE= -0.045), education (EDU= -0.015), and employment status (EMP= -0.034), except for residential location (RLO= 0.016), which has a very weak positive correlation.

Age and Informal Sector Operators Tax Compliance

Age is one of the demographic factors used in this study to test how it could affect informal sector operators' tax compliance. The mean score for age factors shown in Table 4.1 is 2.354 with a median of 2, and the minimum value of 2 and the maximum value of 4. The

standard deviation of 0.567 showed age distribution is closely dispersed from the mean. Furthermore, the results of correlation revealed there was no strong relationship between AGE and other variables of the study. Table 4.2 shows that tax compliance moves in the same positive direction with AGE, but the strength of their association is very weak. More so, both EMP= 0.004 and RLO= 0.012 have a positive but very weak association with AGE. While EDU=-0.017 and GEN=-0.045 both move in opposite directions with AGE, the strength of their association was very weak. It shows that age has a positive but very weak correlation with informal sector operators' tax compliance. The very weak correlation indicates that age does not predict changes in tax compliance.

Education and Informal Sector Operators Tax Compliance

Linking education to tax compliance, the descriptive statistic results in Table 4.1 revealed the mean score for EDU= 4.251 with a minimum score of 2 and a maximum score of 6. The median was 4, and the standard deviation of 0.705. The standard deviation revealed that data for education were closely clustered around the mean and that most of the respondents obtained the educational qualification coded as 4. To understand the association between education and other demographic factors, Table 4.2 presents the correlation results. The correlation result for

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

education and tax compliance showed a very weak positive association. That is, personal income tax compliance has an impact on educational qualifications (0.053). The correlation between EDU and AGE= -0.017, GEN= -0.145, RLO= -0.023 showed a very weak negative association. However, the strength of association between EDU and EMP= 0.019 was found to be positive, but the strength of the association was very weak and close to zero. The result indicates that there is a significant positive relationship between education and informal sector operators' tax compliance. Therefore, education can predict changes in tax compliance.

Employment Status and Informal Sector Operators' Tax Compliance

In describing employment status data in Table 4.1, the mean value was 1.164 with a median of 1, while the minimum value was 1 and the maximum value of 2. The standard deviation score was 0.371, indicating that the data on employment status were closely clustered around the mean. In examining the association among the variables, Table 4.2 presents the correlation matrix between employment status and personal income tax compliance, AGE, EDU, GEN and RLO. The result revealed that EMP was positively correlated with TC= 0.081, AGE= 0.004, and EDU= 0.019, but the strength of the associations was very weak. While the EMP association with GEN= -0.034 and RLO= -0.030 revealed a weak strength of negative correlation. The result shows that a positive correlation exists between employment status and informal sector operators' tax compliance. Therefore, employment status can predict changes in tax compliance.

Residential Location/Government Presence and Informal Sector Operators Tax Compliance

From Table 4.1, the mean of RLO was 1.733 with a standard deviation of 0.443, which was

found to be far from the mean. This implies that the demographic data for residential location/government presence were clustered around the mean. The median of 2 showed that most of the respondents scored 2 points on the scale that measured the residential location/government presence, where the minimum score was 1 and the maximum score of 2. The correlation matrix presented in Table 4.2 revealed the direction and the strength of association between RLO and other demographic factors. AGE= 0.018 and GEN= 0.016 revealed a positive but very weak association with RLO. Where TC= -0.071, EDU= -0.024, EMP= -0.030 showed a weak negative association with RLO. The result indicates that a positive but very weak relationship exists between residential location/government presence and informal sector operators' tax compliance. Therefore, residential location does not influence tax compliance.

Table 4.3: Demographic factors and informal sector operators' tax compliance regression model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
GEN	-0.131027	0.130499	-1.004045	0.3154
AGE	0.010245	0.112923	0.090728	0.9277
EDU	0.558446	0.111021	5.030093	0.0001
EMP	0.419125	0.146672	2.857557	0.0097
RLO	-0.191055	0.144699	-1.320361	0.1867
Limit Points				
LIMIT_2:C(6)	0.143364	0.610048	0.235004	0.8142
Pseudo R-squared	0.711890	Akaike info criterion		1.399308
Schwarz criterion	1.460325	Log likelihood		-266.8650
Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.423495	Restr. log likelihood		-270.0761
LR statistic	8.422194	Avg. log likelihood		-0.684269
Prob (LR statistic)	0.267277			

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2024

In Table 4.3, it was observed from the pooled Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression that the R² value of 0.711890 indicated 71.2% of the methodical variations in informal sector operators' tax compliance, which was explained jointly by the demographic factors. This implies that of the variation in informal sector operators' tax compliance, demographic factors explain only 71.2%. Thus, 8.8% of the variation could not be accounted for by the demographic factors. The LR statistic of 8.422 with the p-value of 0.042 clearly indicated that the model is good at describing compliance. In other words, the overall model is statistically significant in the prediction of personal income tax compliance. As regards the prediction of the impact of gender differences on tax compliance, we utilized the regression result on GEN as presented in Table 4.3. The OLS result revealed that gender diversity appears to explain about 13.1% (-0.131; p=0.32) in informal sector operators' tax compliance. This implies that a change in gender

differences reduces tax compliance by about 13.1%. The z-statistic score of -1.004 also supported that there was a negative cause-and-effect relationship between GEN and TC. However, the probability test value of 0.315 predicted that the regression was statistically insignificant even at a 10% level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis on gender, which stated no significant relationship between gender and informal sector operators' tax compliance, was accepted.

In Table 4.3, the regression coefficient of 0.010 with a probability value greater than 5% (p= 0.93) shows that age as a demographic factor has a progressive but insignificant impact on compliance. Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that no significant correlation exists between age and informal sector operators' tax compliance was accepted owing to the high probability value of 0.93. Based on the results of this study, age does not predict whether a person is going to be tax

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

compliant because of the insignificant regression coefficient of 0.010.

The OLS result in Table 4.3 showed that education predicts about a 55.5% change in tax compliance. The result showed the influence of education on compliance is statistically significant at 5% level of significance, as shown by $OLS = 0.558(p=0.0001)$. Hence, the hypothesis which stated that no correlation exists between education and compliance is rejected, owing to a low probability value (< 0.05). The OLS result in Table 4.3 revealed that employment status predicted about 41.9% change in tax compliance. The statistical inference from the $OLS = 0.4191(p=0.0097)$ showed a significant relationship between employment status and tax compliance at 5% level of significance. In other words, statistically, employment status predicts a change in tax compliance. Thus, the hypothesis, which stated that no correlation exists between employment status and informal sector operators' tax compliance, was rejected.

Table 4.3 also revealed that residential location/government presence $OLS -0.191(p=0.19)$, that is, only 19.1% of total variation in compliance could be attributable to residential location/government presence, but the outcome was statistically insignificant at 10% level of significance. Based on the statistical results of this study, the hypothesis which stated there is no correlation between residential location/government presence and informal sector operators' tax compliance was accepted, owing to the large p-value shown by the analysis.

Limitations

The limitations of this research work are as follows: (a) it is restricted to five variables; (b) the territorial limit of the research is exclusively restricted to the South-south geographical zone of Nigeria; and (c) it is restricted to only the informal sector of the

Nigerian economy. This research is restricted to five variables; a similar study can be conducted using more than five variables, which may suggest findings different from ours. Therefore, more variables should be employed for further studies. This study is also restricted to the South-South zone out of the six geographical zones in Nigeria. Therefore, future studies can be conducted by expanding the geographical zones. This study is focused on the informal sector of the Nigerian economy. Further studies can look at different industries in other sectors of the Nigerian economy.

Contribution to knowledge

Most researchers investigated employment status as a demographic factor and found that assessable income from self-employment occupation is more susceptible to under-reporting for tax purposes than assessable income from employment occupation. Thus, the result of this study is in accord with this assertion. However, the study went a step further to examine 'self-employed' (i.e. unregistered and unregulated operators) with employees operating in the informal sector who deduct taxes from the salaries of such employees, and found that most of them do not remit such taxes to the relevant tax authority. We contributed to existing knowledge by finding that there are two dimensions to employment status. That is, the self-employed (with employees) not only under-report income but also fail to remit taxes deducted from the employees' salaries, resulting in 'double tax evasion. This contribution has expanded the frontier of 'employment status as a demographic factor by the inclusion of non-remittance of deducted taxes.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study investigated selected demographic factors that could have an impact on informal sector operators' tax compliance in Nigeria.

Indeed, tax compliance has recently occupied the front burner of most research carried out in several emerging economies and developed countries, because of the necessity to increase the revenue base of the government rather than borrow to finance its budgets. In line with extant literature, gender as a demographic factor was examined, and our findings suggest that gender does not considerably impact tax compliance in Nigeria. However, literature on gender has produced inconsistent and varied results. It can therefore be argued that such results could be due to differences in the socio-political environment.

The negative relationship that exists between age and informal sector operators' tax compliance suggests a pointer to further investigate how age as a demographic factor can influence informal sector operators' tax compliance. Again, results from most of the findings in the literature are contradictory. It could also be argued that the different legal, socio-political environments and lack of uniformity in sample size could be responsible for such contradictory results. Education plays an important role in influencing tax compliance. Our results revealed a positive relationship between education and informal sector operators' tax compliance. Literature on education has also produced mixed results. It therefore revealed the influence of education on tax compliance to be inconsistent and ambiguous. Such inconsistency and ambiguity could be traced to different variables employed, operationalization of such variables and the lack of ability to identify the aspect of education at a point in time that is being measured.

The result of the study also showed that a positive correlation exists between employment status and informal sector operators' tax compliance. It was also revealed that a negative correlation exists

between residential location/government presence and informal sector operators' tax compliance. Thus, it shows that payment of taxes is not dependent on the provision of basic infrastructure by the government in one's locality.

Having carried out the study on the impact of demographic factors on tax compliance in Nigeria's informal sector: The case study of the South-South geopolitical zone, the following recommendations are proffered:

1. There should be a tax census of the informal sector by the government to enable it to have an accurate database of taxpayers in that sector. This can be achieved by giving incentives in the form of loans to the informal sector operators. For instance, when the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) wants to give out loans to operators in the informal sector, it must make sure that such self-employed operators in the informal sector are registered and well-documented before the disbursement of such loans. This procedure will help to ensure that there is an accurate database of the operators in the informal sector. With such databases, the government can register such informal sector operators and regulate their activities. It will also help to address the prevailing economic hardship experienced in the country. In fact, if the informal sector is empowered, it will boost economic activities and have a multiplier effect on the economy. Then the informal sector operators will willingly pay their taxes, which will, in turn, increase the tax revenue of the government.
2. The government should tilt towards an informal-driven economy to create more employment opportunities and generate more tax revenues. This can be achieved by the government empowering operators in the informal sector and providing an enabling business environment (especially power in terms of stable electricity).
3. Tax education should be incorporated in secondary and tertiary institutions to inculcate

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

the culture of paying taxes as good citizens in our students who are future potential taxpayers. This can be done by the policy makers or formulators by ensuring that the National Assembly or State Houses of Assembly pass a bill into law to teach taxation as a course in the secondary schools, and the inclusion of taxation in General Studies in tertiary institutions. Tax education will positively influence tax compliance.

4. There should be enforcement of tax laws for any infraction by the self-employed, especially those who evade tax and fail to remit deducted taxes to the relevant tax authority. This will influence tax compliance.

5. There should be improvement in awareness, especially for those in the informal sector, because huge potential tax revenue accruable to the government is locked up in that sector. This can be done by organizing 'town hall' meetings with stakeholders, seminars, and sensitization through the mass and electronic media. This will positively impact tax compliance.

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